

SOCIALIZATION OF CHILDREN IN MODERN SOCIETY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10351537>

Key words: children, socialization, society, social networks, video games.

Annotation

This article examines the problem of socialization of modern youth. The author describes this process in detail, paying attention to the opinions of scientists. An attempt has been made to consider the characteristic stages of socialization that correspond to certain life periods. The author pays special attention to socialization channels, paying special attention to the Internet. It is formulated that in connection with the development of society, people of the older generation are actively entering the Internet space. Active analysis of social networks shows how the Internet influences the development of youth.

The society of the 21st century is rapidly developing, and after this, people's perception of the world around them is changing. The process of socialization in the era of the information society takes place differently than at previous stages of world development.

The French sociologist E. Durkheim was one of the first to pay attention to the issue of socialization. He emphasized that any society strives to mold a person in accordance with his ideals, which depend on moral, intellectual, as well as physical development. Socialization is a certain process of assimilation and reproduction by an individual of social, cultural, spiritual experience, which is transmitted by the older generation.

The process of socialization begins from the moment a person is born and continues throughout his entire life. Why is socialization so important? Firstly, this process makes it clear how this person will grow up, and secondly, during the period of socialization, a person learns to communicate with other people, tries on different roles. Thanks to the active interaction of people with each other, individuals form their own beliefs, habits, principles - everything that determines the uniqueness of a person, thus turning him into an individual.

Normal human development is possible only in contact with other people. Loneliness and isolation from society inhibit socialization. A child must have close contact with at least one adult and learn life experience from him. As a rule, support from other people is very important for any person, so adults should build a "bridge of trust" with their son or daughter, thanks to which they can understand and communicate with each other.

American social psychologist D. Mead argued that society interacts with the individual, which means there can be no "I" separate from the outside world. As stated earlier, children "reconcile" different roles, in connection with this and this theory, the younger generation, playing games, pretending to be adults, adopts from them certain behavior and communication styles. Later, grown-up children no longer play a role; they project everything that they learned earlier into the relationships that they develop. When completing a task at school, a student must apply all the knowledge he has received. At the same time, working in a

group is very important, so children learn to find a compromise in the presence of different opinions, and also develop leadership qualities and team management.

You need to understand that along with the concept of socialization there is such a concept as socialization. What is it? The semantic meaning of this word is that a person meets the social requirements that apply to a certain age group. In this regard, it is worth noting the stages of socialization, which include:

1. Early stage (lasts from the moment of birth until admission to an educational institution);
2. Stage of training (starts when entering school, ends at the stage of completing full-time vocational education);
3. Stage of social maturity;
4. Stage of completion of the life cycle (from the moment of employment).

So you can understand that these stages correspond to the age periodization of a person's life accepted in society, namely childhood, adolescence, maturity, old age. There are channels of socialization, which include: family, children's educational institutions, school, friends, the media, the Internet. The latter prevails in the modern world.

The Internet is an integral part of the information society; it is a worldwide network that has embraced and united almost the entire population of the globe. An analysis of statistical data for 2019 shows that in Russia 94.4 million people over 12 years old used the Internet, but this figure is growing every year. So in 2020, the average number of network users was 95.6 million. This is explained by a number of many factors, firstly, the pandemic forced the switch to remote work, and secondly, technological progress, a situation in which the younger generation often changes gadgets, giving previous models to their grandmothers and grandfathers, promotes the involvement of the older generation in social networks. So, according to the data, in 2020 the number of representatives of the 65+ category increased from 26 to 36%, and the 50-64 year old category from 63 to 66%.

In order to more accurately understand how the Internet influences human socialization, it is necessary to conduct social statistics, namely, establish statistical observation. By which we mean systematic, systematic and scientifically based work to collect mass data on the phenomena of sociocultural life by recording essential features according to a predetermined program. Data about each received observation unit obtained as a result of official statistical recording are primary information, and their system forms a set of primary information.

Looking at social statistics, you can see which social networks predominate. TikTok is in great demand among the population. However, according to most experts and psychologists, this Internet space leads to the fact that children at an immature age develop more material values, rather than spiritual ones. Procrastination penetrates into the human consciousness more and more. Many people begin to get angry at everyone around them and ask the question - why can't I do this? What's stopping me from making videos and making money from it? Thus, the normal education and profession familiar to everyone fade into the background, and sometimes are completely forgotten. Children and adults do not go further along the path of socialization, do not develop their thinking, because this activity does not require special thought processes. Infantility is increasing. However, despite the disadvantages, in my opinion, socialization is still possible. Why? While engaging in this

activity, people one way or another have to communicate with society, subscribers, and fellow bloggers in order to create joint content.

YouTube is a media space where you can find almost any information. Starting from entertaining content and ending with educational and informative content. However, this platform is also dangerous for the development and formation of personality. Why? There is a variety of content, including prohibited content. The Ministry of Justice maintains a registry of extremist materials, which often includes YouTube content. The process of removing these materials from this social network is quite difficult; therefore, it can reach minors and adults and affect their consciousness. In our opinion, this platform will be a very good step in the socialization of people, because thanks to it you can find your calling, including benefiting society. Reading poetry, posting travel video content from different countries, learning foreign languages - all this helps a person in the modern world.

COVID-19 has forced people to transfer their activities to the Internet. Video conferencing, webinars, and online education have begun to develop more and more. If you look at this situation from two sides, then in the first case there is an Internet assistant, thanks to which people were able to continue their work, thanks to it the program "Digital Economy" approved back in 2017 began to develop. On the other hand, the process of personal interaction between people has weakened. In the modern world, people increasingly prefer SMS, telephone communication, and ZOOM meetings.

Thus, the process of socialization in modern society is not limited only to communicating with people, it also includes searching for new information on the Internet, reading books, watching TV, reviewing news, and video games. However, we must understand that a person can only fully socialize among other members of society. We need communication, adoption of other people's experience, because thanks to this we can avoid mistakes and rash actions.

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